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XALQARO JURNALI**

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TIL, TA'LIM, TARJIMA ЯЗЫК, ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ, ПЕРЕВОД LANGUAGE, EDUCATION, TRANSLATION

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REPRESENTATION OF LINGUOCULTUREMES IN ENGLISH TOURISM DISCOURSE

ABSTRACT

This article discusses the importance of Linguoculturology as a new branch of Modern Linguistics and its role in English tourism discourse. More importantly, it explores different types of linguoculturemes including realia, toponyms, anthroponyms, metaphor and other stylistic devices as cultural models that are frequently observed in English tourism promotion websites. The research further analyzes the communicative strategies and rhetoric devices to show how language matters not only in representing culture, but also in skillfully attracting the potential tourists to tourist destinations in tourism discourse as a marketing strategy. The research results contribute to not only linguistics, but also linguoculturology, discourse studies, tourism, marketing, and intercultural communication.

Keywords: linguocultureme, realia, toponyms, stylistic devices, tourism discourse, rhetoric devices

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РЕПРЕЗЕНТАЦИЯ ЛИНГВОКУЛЬТУРЕМ В АНГЛОЯЗЫЧНОМ ТУРИСТИЧЕСКОМ ДИСКУРСЕ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье рассматривается важность лингвокультурологии как новой ветви современной лингвистики и её роль в англоязычном туристическом дискурсе. Более того, исследуются различные типы лингвокультурных образов, включая реалии, топонимы, антропонимы, метафоры и другие стилистические приёмы, как культурные модели, часто встречающиеся на англоязычных сайтах, посвящённых продвижению туризма. Исследование также анализирует коммуникативные стратегии и риторические

приёмы, чтобы показать, как язык важен не только для представления культуры, но и для умелого привлечения потенциальных туристов в туристические места в рамках туристического дискурса как маркетинговой стратегии. Результаты исследования вносят вклад не только в лингвистику, но и в лингвокультурологию, дискурсивные исследования, туризм, маркетинг и межкультурную коммуникацию.

Ключевые слова: лингвокультура, реалии, топонимы, стилистические приемы, туристический дискурс, риторические приемы

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INGLIZ TURIZM DISKURSIDA LINGVOKULTUREMALARNING IFODALANISHI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqola Lingvomadaniyatshunoslikning zamonaviy tilshunoslikning yangi tarmog'ini sifatidagi ahamiyati va uning turizm diskursidagi o'rnini muhokama qiladi. Ahamiyatli shundaki, bu maqola realia, antroponim va toponimlarni o'z ichiga olgan turli xil lingvokulturemalarni hamda ingliz turizm saytlarida ko'p uchraydigan metafora va boshqa stilistik vositalarni madaniy birlik sifatida o'rganadi. Bundan tashqari tadqiqot muloqot strategiyalar va ritorik vositalarni ham tahlil qiladi va bu orqali til nafaqat madaniyatni namoyon etishda qanchalik ahamiyatga ega ekanligi, balki marketing strategiyasi sifatida ham turizm diskursida turistlarni sayohat manzillariga mohirona jalb etishda tilning ahamiyatini ko'rsatadi. Tadqiqot natijalari esa nafaqat lingvistika, lingvomadaniyatshunoslik, diskurs, madaniyatlararo muloqot, balki turizm hamda marketing sohalariga ham hissa qo'shadi.

Kalit so'zlar: lingvokulturema, realia, toponimlar, stilistik vositalar, turizm diskursi, ritorik vositalar

Before the emergence of Linguoculturology as an independent discipline, its core principles are usually attributed to E. Sapir and B.L. Whorf, who are often recognized as foundational figures for the birth of modern linguoculturology. Although they did not use the term 'linguoculturology', they initially studied the theoretical relationship between language, culture, cognition, thought and worldview, discussing the notions of linguistic relativity, cultural worldview, ethnolinguistic cognition. They were the first advocates of the view that language is not only a means of communication, but it is a cultural and cognitive system via which humans understand the world. In other words, human thought is influenced by language and culture. Each language reflects a unique worldview, speakers of different languages, thus, perceive the reality differently. One more proof of the close connection between language and culture Sapir provides is that the cultural experience of nations is reflected in their vocabulary system (language). Ultimately, their ideas became the core principles of linguocultural analysis [23, B. 26; 4, B. 433-435].

Novel conceptualizations of language have already centered the attention of linguists in the XXI century. According to these ideas, language is not merely a means of

communication, but it is also a carrier of cultural information, serving as the cultural code of nations. This is usually attributed to the emergence and development of a new anthropocentric paradigm, a human-centered framework that prioritizes human as the most important unity and studies 'human factor' in language. It concentrates on the idea that as human is the core foundation of the universe and language, he is the only carrier, transmitting universal and nationally-specific values of people across generations [3, B.10]. Similarly, Yu. S. Stepanov emphasizes the idea that language does not exist without a person. According to his theory, there are three components of language: system, human, and culture. By analyzing constants – stable concepts shaped by culture, he showed the relationship between language, human, and culture. Since, these constants usually prevail in the human mind, and they are verbalized through language [24, B. 56].

Ashurova and Galieva argue that language is not only a bearer of knowledge, but it is a particular conceptual system, via which human beings interpret the world, cognize, and conceptualize the reality and culture [2, B. 17]. A lot of contemporary research is being carried out in linguistics within the framework of this paradigm, development of which gave rise to many transformations in linguistic views, approaches and methods of analysis, more importantly – the birth of modern interdisciplinary trends in linguistics including Linguoculturology, Gender Linguistics, Cognitive Linguistics, Sociolinguistics, Psycholinguistics, etc. These new disciplines center on the connection between language and culture, language and mind, language and society [3, B.14].

Linguoculturology is one of such newly appeared linguistic disciplines, brought about by the anthropocentric paradigm. Although its main focus is to study language and culture, with its interdisciplinary nature, it combines the fields beyond linguistics and cultural studies, such as cognitive linguistics, ethnolinguistics, and sociolinguistics. Thus, what it mainly investigates is the deep-level semantics of linguistic signs, thereby, it correlates linguistic meanings with the concepts of universal and national cultures [3, B.15].

In the study of Linguoculturology, particularly, Russian linguists stand out with their key contributions to the field. This is best exemplified by the works of the scholars in Russian linguistic school – V.N. Telia, V.V. Karasik, V.A. Maslova, A.A. Potebnya, N.D. Arutyunova, V. Vorobyov, Yu.S. Stepanov, etc. Although there is no exact year of its evolution, considering the fact that it is a comparatively new discipline, we can mark its evolution into two periods: the first stage is the formation of theoretical ideas that became basis for anthropocentric paradigm and cultural linguistics. This period encompasses the works by W. von. Humboldt, E. Sapir, and B. Whorf from western linguistics. The second stage, started in the 90th of the XX century, is the period when Linguoculturology was officially became an independent discipline – an independent branch of linguistics, thanks to the works by Russian scholars. Take V.N. Telia, one of those first scholars to propose Linguoculturology to be a scientific discipline, for instance; she argued that language and culture should be studied together, not in isolation. By analyzing phraseological units from linguacultural perspective, she emphasized that linguistic meaning cannot be interpreted outside the cultural knowledge. In other words, people understand idioms, proverbs, and other fixed expressions not only by their linguistic meaning, but via the collective cultural knowledge, as these units carry cultural connotations as well, such as traditions, cultural values, history, stereotypes, and national worldview of a people [25, B. 38].

V. Vorobyov [27, B. 37] is another key contributor to the field of Linguoculturology. Beyond defining Linguoculturology as an autonomous field, he explained the object and subject of the discipline, as well as, developed methodological framework for linguacultural analysis. The object of the science is the interaction of language, culture, and human consciousness, while the subject is nationally and culturally specific lexicon that reflect cultural values and people's worldview. He also introduced the concepts of 'linguocultural competence' and 'linguocultural unit' – culturally-marked lexicon including metaphors, idioms, proverbs, symbols, etc. The former, he claims, is needed for successful communication – grammatical competence is not enough. According to his widely-recognized definition about Linguoculturology, it studies "... correlations and interactions between culture and language in their functioning" [27, B. 37].

Of paramount importance is the contribution of V.V. Krasnykh to Cultural Linguistics. She specifically analyzed how culture is represented, manifested and fixed in the language and discourse. What she particularly centered on is the way how culture inherently prevails and functions in our cognition, discourse, and communication process, which makes her work valuable source in terms of linguocultural analysis of discourse. To be more precise, her research revolves around the concepts – linguistic personality, national world picture, cognitive space, precedent phenomena, cognition shaped by culture, mental-lingual complex, and cross-cultural communication frameworks. Unlike earlier scholars who examined primarily lexical units, phraseological units, concepts, and symbols in Linguoculturology, she placed so much importance to discourse as the object of her research, beyond grammar, vocabulary, and text structure. Culture, she claims, is never static, but rather it is always shaped dynamically in discourse. Thus, language is not sufficient for analysis, it is discourse – the authentic process where culture is formed and functions. In other words, full linguacultural analysis can only be made in discourse, considering the fact that manifests cultural knowledge, mentality, ethnocultural values, nationality, stereotypes, and worldview of the peoples [16, B.27]. One of the important contributions she made is the precedent phenomena theory she developed. It refers to the culturally-relevant phenomena, including precedent names, texts, situations, utterances that members of a linguistic community share (To be or not to be, Big Brother, Romeo and Juliet for English discourse; Pushkin, War and Peace, biblical references for Russian Discourse; Alisher Navai, Alpomish, Muslim traditions for Uzbek discourse) When these precedent units are utilized in discourse, they trigger cultural memory, shred cultural associations, background knowledge about the nation and culture. Culture itself usually categorizes the world via different cultural codes: somatic, spatial, temporal, biomorphic, spiritual, and object codes. Thus, each discourse can encompass various cultural codes. Equally important in her analysis is the term 'linguistic personality'. By this term, she does not merely refer to an interlocutor, but a carrier of cultural information. Given that discourse reveals personality, cultural and national identity, mentality, and ethnic worldview of the speaker, of utmost importance in discourse analysis to pay attention to who is speaking, and from which cultural perspective they are speaking [16, B.27].

Of utmost importance is the interdisciplinary nature of Linguoculturology. It refers to "the correlation of two or more sciences on the basis of the common theoretical assumptions, notions and methods of analysis" [3, B.12]. Interdisciplinarity can be of two types: internal and external. The former refers to the interface between such linguistic disciplines as

phonetics, lexicology, morphology, syntax, stylistics, etc., while the latter is linked with the modern trends of linguistics including Cognitive Linguistics, Linguopragmatics, Psycholinguistics, Sociolinguistics, Literary criticism, Linguoculturology, Ethnolinguistics, Intercultural communication, etc [1, B.20]. The main purpose behind interdisciplinarity, they state, is not about just transmitting principal ideas, and approaches of one discipline into another, but with its effective cooperation, it aims to propose solutions to new problems, considering that multidisciplinary is all about paying special attention to humans and all realms of human activity. Linguoculturology, therefore, is marked by both internal and external interdisciplinarity (linguistic and non-linguistic). In external one, it creates close connection with such disciplines as History, Sociology, Anthropology, Culturology, Theology and Philosophy, etc., as deep-level semantics of culturally-specific linguistic signs cannot be examined without taking into consideration religious, historical, social, etc. factors. Furthermore, Ashurova and Galieva [3, B.15] single out five main trends of Cultural Linguistics: lexicographical, phraseological, conceptological, stylistic, and comparative. Why linguocultural lexicography matters so much in this science is that it compiles dictionaries which represent cultural specificity, culture-relevant events and phenomena belonging to a certain linguoculture. For instance: toponyms (geographical names), anthroponyms (names of famous historical/religious figures), holidays, traditions, history, mythology, folklore, and specific terms related to the political and economic systems, etc. [3, B.16]. Phraseological units are also one of the important layers of national world picture as they are charged with cultural connotations, national mentality, and cultural values [17, B.69; 25, B.31; 21, B.86; 15, B.110; 3, B. 78].

Central to the linguoculturology is the notion of concept, which is an essential part of national, linguistic, and conceptual world pictures. Each concept can be shaped by individual's emotional, physical, historical, personal, and social background and experience gained in the process of understanding the world [21, B.55]. Thus, concepts usually belong to either an individual linguistic world picture or the whole linguocultural community [3, B.73]. Stylistics, widely-recognized as a "human-oriented" discipline, is influenced by Cultural Linguistics, as stylistic devices play a paramount role in the representation of cultural concepts. Therefore, SDs usually serve as cultural models, or image-bearing linguistic units which are charged with national-cultural specificity. The last direction is Comparative Cultural Linguistics, which deals with the comparative and contrastive analysis of culturally-marked units of different linguocultures [3, B.35].

Of utmost importance in Linguoculturology is the notion of linguocultureme or linguocultural units. It is basically a linguistic unit which carries cultural information beyond its literary sense. Some of the common examples of linguoculturemes are phoenix, paradise, White House, pub, etc. A lot of research on the classification of the sources of the linguoculturemes, and their structural, semantic features has been conducted by various scholars. Particularly, works of V.A. Maslova, V.V. Vorobyov, Yuri. S. Stepanov, V.I. Karasik, D.U. Ashurova and M.R. Galieva are worth mentioning. Built on these scholars' works, we can say that there are different sources of linguoculturemes, ranging from everyday realias, lacunas, myths, legends, speech etiquette, symbols and images to traditions, customs, literature, superstitions, historical events, literary and religious facts [27, B.56; 21, B.97; 3, B.15].

Realias (non-equivalent lexicon) of everyday life are the words which have no direct equivalence or translation in another language, therefore, very specific to a certain culture. Images can be illustrated by the use of particular stylistic devices, such as metaphors, similes, euphemisms, symbols, antonomasia, etc. Another source of linguocultural units is speech etiquette formulas including greetings, agreement, disagreement, compliment, condolences, revealing politeness strategies belonging to a certain linguoculture [6, B.9; 10, B.13]. Myths are expressed by mythologemes [3, B.15]. Phraseological units, symbols, quotations, aphorisms also inherently reflect the nationality, customs, lifestyles, religious beliefs, literature, and history of different peoples [25, B.78]. According to Ashurova and Galieva [3, B.57-58], linguoculturemes can be verbalized by a word, a word combination, a paragraph or a whole text. For example, the word *pub* means “a public house” in its literary sense (linguistic meaning). However, this word carrier great cultural significance for the English. In Britain, for instance, pubs are considered as the places where people get together to relax, chat, spend evenings in a good company after a tiring day or discuss business or political issues in a more convenient atmosphere. Many other examples, such as *lady*, *lord*, *gentleman* can be observed in English discourse, while words like *mahalla*, *choykhona*, *plov* can be seen in Uzbek discourse. Word combinations including *husband's tea*, *English breakfast*, *a small talk* can represent English culture, while phrases like *beshik to'y*, *kelin ko'rishar* can reflect Uzbek culture. Similarly, linguoculturemes can be expressed by a paragraph or a text (both micro and macrotects) as well [3, B.60-73].

A. Wierzbicka [28, B.6] also made similar research regarding the linguoculturemes although she did not use the term ‘linguocultureme’. According to her, each language is composed of culturally significant units, called ‘*key words*’ that reflect essential values, mentality, worldview, and communicative rules of a particular community or group of people. Such words are not simple lexical units, but culturally grounded concepts that show the way people understand emotions, relationships, nationality, moral and social behavior, etc. Many of such key words (linguoculturemes), therefore, have no full equivalent or translation in other languages considering meanings of such words are deeply rooted in culture [28, B.6-10].

The reason why discourse matters so much in linguoculturology is the fact that different sizes of linguoculturemes serve as culturally-marked units within discourse, or discourse reflects culture through the use of linguoculturemes. V.V. Krasnkh and V.N. Telia further expanded linguocultural analysis toward discourse and communication process, where cultural meaning is encoded dynamically in interaction [16, B.99, 25, B.55].

Many scholars conducted linguocultural analysis of discourse in a different manner based on the types of discourse. N.Y. Bobrova, for instance, conducted linguocultural analysis of the literary discourse of J.Updike. By analyzing his short stories as the object of the research, she identified cultural paradigm used in Updike's discourse. She also found out that cultural paradigm is revealed explicitly by the use of mostly toponyms, realias, and other nationally-specific words which usually evoke certain associations of setting of the story, lifestyle of the people, and implicitly by the forms of address, and relationships among the characters in the story [5, B.4-5].

I. Goshkheteliani & A. Kalandia also investigated the linguocultural peculiarities of specifically, tourism discourse, paying special attention to the vocabulary choice, languaging, and other communicative and persuasive techniques, frequently applied in this discourse,

thereby conducting a contrastive analysis of English-Georgian tourism discourse. They conclude that discourse (not only tourism discourse) is dynamic; thus, the nationality, culture, and history of both nations are reflected and compared via the use of different linguistic choices and communicative strategies (linguocultures). Thus, studying the linguocultural peculiarities of tourism discourse which usually speaks of the culture of different nations, they state, helps understand the intercultural communication, and avoid misunderstandings beyond contributing to translation studies and teaching tourism vocabulary [12, B.20].

English tourism discourse has been the focus of studies for the last two decades, especially attracting the attention of those scholars investigating the persuasive language used in tourism discourse to promote a certain product or service and influence the purchasing behavior of consumers by means of persuasive language (manipulation) as a marketing strategy. As English serves as the lingua franca of tourism, it is essential to understand the modern trends of persuasive communication both that the linguistic and discursive level [19, B.16] Yet, tourism discourse has more than just a promotional purpose – social and cultural information characteristic of different nations are reflected, which makes it worth investigating [20, B.7]. Persuasive strategies employed in tourism communication by different cultures/countries also vary, as each nation targets members of different cultures based on their sociocultural perspective. So, the literature highlights different scholars who studied various persuasive means and linguocultures used in English tourism discourse to attract potential visitors and promote tourist destinations. U. Nasritdinov explores toponyms in English tourism materials, and he emphasizes the function of toponyms in tourism discourse beyond just naming places – storytelling, referencing, increasing the cultural, historical, and geographical appeal of destinations. In other words, **toponyms** usually function as linguocultures, carrying cultural information besides its core function. As a persuasive tool, the use of toponyms can strengthen destination branding and cultural identity, fostering a closer connection between tourists and the places they visit. This is best exemplified by some English toponyms such as Stonehenge, the Grand Canyon, and the Lake District, which evoke the feelings of natural beauty, historical awe, and cultural uniqueness [22, B.323]. So, toponyms in English tourism discourse have three functions – emotional appeal, representation of cultural identity, and destination branding technique. N. Iritspukhova investigates the role of metaphor in English tourism promotional discourse, highlighting the discursive, conceptual, and cultural elements metaphor carries within a cross-cultural communication. The primary function of metaphor used in tourism promotional discourse is to reduce the unfamiliarity of a particular destination by describing physically or culturally distant places not only special and extraordinary, but close to ordinary experiences [9, B.32; 14, B.67]. Being compact in nature, metaphor is usually designed to be attractive, memorable, and eye-catching to the readers, more importantly, it can convey several meanings in a single phrase. Similarly, S. Francesconi [11, B.178-183] focuses on the theoretical and pragmatic employment of metaphors of jewels (jewel metaphors refer to the metaphors, the source domains of which are represented by *precious stones*, such as *gems, gold, emeralds, pearls, turquoise, etc.*) as a rhetoric means, and explored ideological manipulation of time through these metaphors by analyzing tourist promotional catalogues. These metaphors that emphasizes the impressive beauty and values of places are actually very prevalent in tourism discourse. Accordingly, R. Hallet and J. Kaplan-Weinger [13, B.27] also highlight metaphor as a discursive strategy that usually serves as a narrative device in tourism-related texts, often

forming tourist and destination identity. In other words, it is the metaphor, with the help of which tourism websites usually build and promote regional and social identity of a particular place. Take, for instance, the metaphor used in Luisiana's official destination website; before the hurricane, Luisiana was described as LUISIANA IS FOOD, LUISIANA IS DIVERSITY, which formed the identity of this state as a culturally diverse state. Yet, after the disaster, this place started to be described using such different metaphors as LUISIANA IS PHOENIX, LUISIANA IS REBORN, which reflects the physical destruction of the city by natural disasters, and calls the tourists for social action to restore the society [13, B.27]. Besides, hyperbolic and personification metaphors are quite common in tourism discourse [14, B.72].

Of equal importance is the work by M. Buzrukova [7, B.1753], who studied metaphor frequently observed in tourism discourse, and classified it into different types. She defines metaphor as a mental model that bridges abstract and concrete domains, enabling readers (potential tourists), visitors, and tourism professionals to understand new or complex phenomena through familiar conceptual structures. According to her, six types of metaphor prevail in tourism discourse:

1. Structural metaphor. It helps tourists understand tourism products, services, and experiences through the concepts taken from everyday human activity and experience: *room block, full house*. *Room block* refers to a number of rooms in a hotel reserved in advance for a group of tourists. Source domain: room in a house; Target domain: room in a hotel. Here, through the unified spatial unit – block, a number of hotel rooms are referred. Full house means that all the rooms in a hotel are occupied, no room is available. Source domain: home and household; Target domain: hotel occupancy. The metaphorical mapping is HOTEL IS HOUSE.

2. Directional metaphor. This type refers to the metaphorical expressions related to location or movement through time and space in tourism communication: *gateway city, cultural compass*. *Gateway city* serves as the main entry point to a region, country or a travel destination. Source domain: gate, doorway, entrance; Target domain: destination access or arrival point. Here, the conceptual mapping is ENTERING THROUGH A DESTINATION IS PASSING THROUGH A GATE, or A CITY IS A GATEWAY. The directional point is moving from outside into inside. The next example is *cultural compass*, which means a metaphorical guide that helps tourists understand local traditions, customs, values, and cultural practices. Source domain: physical compass that is used for navigating; Target domain: guide for cultural understanding. The mapping is UNDERSTANDING CULTURE IS COMPASS, or CULTURAL KNOWLEDGE IS COMPASS.

3. Ontological metaphor. This type of metaphor represents abstract notions with more concrete “living” characteristics. It is also called personification metaphor by some scholars. For example: *heart of the city, living culture*. In *heart of the city*, physical heart in the center of a human body is source domain, while the city is the target domain. The city is conceptualized as a living organism. Thus, THE HEART OF THE ORGANISM IS THE CITY CENTER. Another example is *living culture*. Source domain: living organism; Target domain: culture. Culture is abstract in nature – it has no biological function, or physical body, it does not change or grow, unlike a living being, which can change or adapt over time. So, the conceptual mapping here is CULTURE IS A LIVING ORGANISM.

4. Synesthetic metaphor. By using different senses, this type of metaphor creates vivid and memorable descriptions of travel experiences, ultimately evoking a deeper emotional

connection the described place or object: *palette of flavors, scented hues*. In *palette of flavors*, source domain is palette of diverse colors (vision), while the target domain is flavor (taste). So, the conceptual blending here is FLAVORS ARE COLORS. Another example is *scented hues*. Color is the source domain in this example as well, while the target domain is scent, which is conceptualized as SCENTS ARE COLORS.

5. Simple metaphor. This sort of metaphor usually employs vivid imagery to make travel destinations, attractions, and experiences more understandable and memorable: *a gem of the sea, an open-air museum, crossroads of cultures, melting pot, tapestry of history, stairway to heaven, etc.* Take *a gem of the sea*, for instance; a coastal destination is compared to a precious stone, thereby transferring the qualities of a gem to a tourist destination. Source domain is the physical gem stone, while target domain is the tourist destination, which implies that A TOURIST DESTINATION IS A GEM.

6. Extended metaphor. A broader metaphorical framework is used to further enrich the description and provide a more immersive experience: the city as a theatre, the lighthouse of civilization. In the former, the city's vibrant street life, historical architecture, and cultural events are compared to a grand stage (theatre), and the tourists can feel like the real actors on this stage, playing ongoing performance. Source domain is the physical theatre and performance, while the target domain is the city life in tourist destination. So, the conceptual mapping is CITY IS THEATRE [7, B.1754].

Stefania M. Maci [19, B.11] further highlighted the role of lexical items, rhetorical strategies, and syntactic structures in achieving certain communicative goals in tourism communication. As a specialized type of discourse, English tourism discourse stands out with its lexicon, which is usually characterized by monoreferentiality – only one meaning is allowed in a given context. It is closely connected with precision and conciseness, encompassing mostly tourism terms that have a lack of emotive function. In monoreferentiality, we can include such linguistic devices as acronyms (*B&B – bed and breakfast, ARC – airline reporting conference, UNWTO – United Nations World Tourism Organization*), abbreviations (*FAM – Familiarization Tour*), zero derivation (such as the nouns *check in* and *check out*, deriving from the phrasal verbs *check in* and *check out*), blending (*campsite – camping site, campground – camping ground*), new coinages (*eco-tour, eco-tourism*), metaphors (*'Move over Iceland! Portugal is stealing your spotlight'*), languaging and lexical borrowings (*cappuccino*), keywords that activate tourists' imagination by mentioning them the main points of the text (*away, adventure, dream, imagination, pleasure, escape, genuine, authentic, real*), etc. Of equal importance are the syntactic features of English tourism discourse. What makes tourism discourse stand out from general discourse is the choice of certain syntactic structures, such as premodification, nominalization, person pronouns, verb tenses, modals, and passive forms. Premodification is the process in which lexical units with adjectival function are left dislocated according to the head noun, and, thereby modifying the qualities of the latter (*inbound tour operator, coffee shop, check-in time*). Nominalization, on the other hand, is the process in which one syntactic category is transformed into another, which makes the meaning precise, specific and straightforward to understand in tourism communication. For instance: *tourist arrivals, to bus*, etc. Ego targeting – the special use of personal pronouns (*be, us, our, you, your*) is one of the efficient persuasive strategies in tourism discourse, as a result of employing it, the readers are easily drawn into the text, and empathy is built, creating

identification and loyalty. It is like creating personal relationship between tourists and tourism institutions, at the same time giving the potential tourists the feeling of unprecedented freedom. “*You can stroll, admire birds, enjoy the paradors restaurant.*” [20, B.12]. Adjectives are of utmost importance especially in English tourism discourse, as they are ideal tools for emphatic and evaluative purposes. Descriptive and evaluative adjectives as *decent facilities, fantastic location, spacious, upper balconies, superb view, etc.* enrich the informative description by positive appraisal and assign certain features as beauty and uniqueness to the described destinations. The meaning is more emphasized especially when they are used in the superlative form: *the country’s largest museum, one of the oldest and finest in the world, etc.* Deixis – reference to time, place and people is also very common in tourism communication as promoted destinations are usually contextualized by it so that potential visitors virtually move from their hometown to the described destination with continuous references to the details related to the context. “*This modern and popular hotel, It’s all here in XXX*” [20, B.34]. As far as the verb tenses concerned, the most frequently employed one in tourist guidebooks, brochures, etc. is the present simple, as it gives a stay in a city in a more extended time span. Imperatives are also mostly applied in tourist brochures and guidebooks as they have the pragmatic purpose of urging tourists to act or make a decision on experiencing a certain tourist attraction. In other words, they serve as a type of speech act (primarily directives, yet suggestive and prescriptive ones are also used to encourage potential tourists to travel). For instance: “*Get another view on London from the London Eye with a glass of champagne.*” Modal verbs are skillfully employed in tourism discourse to show how the world *might* be (truth about the world) or *should* be (judgement about the world). In other words, modality prompts action: you *can* experience something, you *can* buy something, etc. *Must* is often used in a nominalized form (*must-see items, must-visit places*). *Will* indicates epistemic certainty and the promise of the tour operator: “*You will see Bath Abbey and the much-photographed Pulteney Bridge, modelled on the Ponte Vecchio in Florence*” [20, B.35]. Furthermore, beyond metaphorical language, attention-seeking rhetoric devices are also used in tourism slogans, which deviate the readers’ expectations. For instance, humor (*A little pit of Paris in the South Pacific*), irony (*Staff has enough English to purchase from, but perhaps not enough to fully explain what was on offer*), and puns (*Manchester – one-time engine room of the Industrial Revolution – has a new role as a dynamo of British culture*) urges the audience to interpret the joke and give an emotional response, thereby creating a special bond with the tourists [20, B.37].

Of paramount importance in the representation of linguocultural features of tourism discourse is *realia*. It is actually a type of non-equivalent lexicon that encompasses words denoting everyday objects, concepts, situations peculiar to a particular nation, which do not exist in other languages [3, B.72]. Various scholars classified *realia* into different types. According to Vinogradov’s classification, there are six types:

1. Household *realia* – includes the names of clothes, food and drink, house, currency, national holidays, customs, musical instruments, etc.
2. Ethnographic and mythological *realia* – includes anthroponyms and toponyms from myths, folklore, and religious characters.
3. Nature *realia* – encompasses flora and fauna specific to a certain region.

4. Social and political realia – consists of names of social organizations and political parties, classes, legislative and institutional powers.
5. Onomastic realia – includes anthroponyms and toponyms.
6. Associative realia – encompasses animalistic symbols, color symbols, and allusions.

Realia words are considered the most prevalent type of linguocultemes in tourism discourse. O.V. Koliasa et al. [26, B.93]. studied realia and its types observed in tourist guides and dictionaries. Realia related to the gastronomy, history, cultural heritage of a particular nation serves as a means of creating an image of the tourist destination beyond representing its cultural values. They singled out the realia observed in tourism materials into two categories: linguacultural and professional realia. The former is designed to create local color and an attractive image of the country, while the latter acts as a means of representing information about tourist services. Linguacultural realia are subdivided into national, regional and local types. National realia include the names of artifacts that are of national and European significance while regional realia encompass artefacts that are specific to a particular territory or a cultural-historical region. Local ones include realia that are of local significance at the level of a city or one department. Professional realia are quite similar to tourism terms, as they encompass names of official organization in tourism sector of a specific area, i.e. Great Britain, unique product offerings for various categories of tourists [26, B.95].

G. Cappelli [8, B.358] studies another technique called ‘linguaging’ – the use of foreign words to provide local color. It is usually associated with evoking emotions, memory, and reflecting one’s identity with specific sociolinguistic and pragmatic features. Therefore, linguaging gives authenticity to the destinations described and creates a type of ‘linguascap’ that the readers will find at the destination [9, B.14]. It also helps to fill the cultural gap between two nations by providing translations and definitions for the culture-relevant linguistic units and cultural concepts, thereby making the ‘unknown or exotic’ more familiar. Linguaging is usually expressed by different forms of code switching. Yet, some of the words are real lexical borrowings: certain words in English tourism discourse such as *espresso*, *cappuccino*, *pasta*, *vista*, *etc.* have an Italian origin, but are now fully assimilated in the English system and are part of the English lexicon. These sort of words, by nature, build images, expectations, and stereotypes about nations. Thus, this is one more proof of the hypothesis that linguistic choices actually play a fundamental role in tourism discourse [8, B.60; 9, B.17].

Stylistic devices – culture-relevant units also serve as cultural models, conveying certain cultural information and esthetic value to the reader. Although not all the stylistic devices represent culture, the most relevant to cultural specifics are the following groups of stylistic devices according to Ashurova and Galieva [3, B.65]:

- Image-bearing stylistic devices (imagery, metaphor, metonymy, simile, metaphorical epithet, metaphorical periphrasis, symbol, personification, and zoonym)
- Stylistic devices that activate knowledge structures or are based on intertextuality (allusion, antonomasia)
- Stylistic devices, showing the politeness principles (euphemism, litotes).

We analyzed more than 50 tourism promotional text taken from the official website of UK tourism (<https://www.visitbritain.com/en>). The following is the detailed analysis of one of such texts:

It's not just our food festivals turning up the heat this summer. Britain is sizzling with world-class sport, toe-tapping concerts and colourful Pride celebrations – and you're invited to join the party. Have a right royal time at our castles, where jousting knights and outdoor theatre bring Britain's history bang up to date. Or escape to our coast, where you can conquer the King Charles III England Coast Path – the world's longest continual seaside hiking route – or tee off at Scotland's sea-breezy championship links courses. Time for a breather? Tuck into the freshest seafood, explore a Victorian pier or try your luck at rockpooling. One thing's for sure: you'll have (buckets and) spades of fun in Britain this summer [2].

This promotional text is taken from English tourism website for the analysis. The text is packed with realia, and various stylistic and rhetoric devices. We identified the types of realia according to Vinogradov's classification. The following sorts of realia have been observed in the text:

- **natural (geographical) realia:** *links courses*. A link course is a unique natural terrain in Scotland, which serves as the golf course. Thus, this very realia reflects the type of natural land and environment of Scotland.

- **onomastic realia:** *King Charles III England Coast Path, Britain, Scotland's*. By mentioning the anthroponym (King Charles III) and toponyms (Britain, Scotland's), these realia carry cultural and historical information, relevant to the history of British Kingdom.

- **household realia:** *castle, Victorian pier, jousting knights, seafood, rockpooling, Pride celebrations*. These are also examples of household realia that show the type of residence, food, coastal pastime, festival, and holidays, peculiar to Scotland.

- **social and political realia:** *royal, knights*. These realia refer to the specific social class and institutional power (monarchy) in the UK.

Almost all types of realia – linguoculturesemes are used in this tourism discourse (text) to show the cultural historic identity of the UK.

We identified various stylistic devices according to Ashurova and Galieva's typology:

- **metaphor:** *Britain is sizzling, food festivals turning up the heat, conquer the King Charles III England Coast Path, Britain's history bang up to date;*

- **personification:** *Britain is sizzling;*

- **pun:** *(buckets and) spades of fun;*

- **allusion:** *King Charles III, royal time, jousting knights, Victorian pier;*

- **hyperbole:** *world-class sport, freshest seafood;*

- **epithet:** *colorful Pride celebrations, toe-tapping concerts, sea-breezy championship links, freshest seafood, world-class sport;*

- **imagery:** *castles, Victorian pier, colorful Pride celebrations* (visual imagery), *toe-tapping concerts* (auditory), *freshest seafood, sea-breezy championship links courses* (sensory);

The stylistic devices used do not only create emotional impact on the readers, but they also serve as cultural models, manifesting the unique culture and history of the place by intertextuality and the presence of realia.

The following rhetorical devices were employed to attract the readers:
- **ego-targeting (direct address):** the second person pronoun **you** is effectively and repeatedly used to directly address the reader, thereby showing personal involvement and creating

engagement, a sense of freedom, and intimacy between tourists and travel agencies: *you're invited to join the party, you can conquer the King Charles III England Coast Path, you'll have (buckets and) spades of fun.*

- **inclusiveness:** *our food festivals, our castle, our coast.* These inclusive pronouns build shared identity between visitors and travel destination, showcasing Britain as welcoming and hospitable.

- **enumeration:** *world-class sport, toe-tapping concerts and colourful Pride celebrations.* By listing the facilities, diversity and the abundance of attractions is shown.

- **imperatives:** *have a right royal time, escape to our coast, tee off, tuck into the freshest seafood, explore Victorian pier, try your luck at rockpooling.* The use of such imperative structures (directives in speech act) urges the audience to take action, thereby making the text more dynamic and persuasive.

- **rhetoric question:** *Time for a breather?* This is also a powerful persuasive tool, used to prompt the audience to decide to pay a visit.

- **superlatives:** *longest, freshest.* They give the readers the impression of unique experience about the travel destination, showing the exceptional qualities of what is being promoted.

- **evaluative vocabulary:** *colorful, world-class, toe-tapping, outdoor, seaside, sea-breezy, fun, etc.* They give the readers a sense of adventure and extraordinariness, persuading them to visit this place.

According to the analysis of English tourism websites, the most frequently used stylistic devices include imagery, metaphor, epithet, personification, antonomasia, allusion, symbols and hyperbole.

In brief, linguocultural analysis of English tourism discourse is of paramount significance, as tourism communication is where diverse cultures cross. In particular, linguoculturemes – different types of realia, symbols, toponyms, anthroponyms, stylistic devices as cultural models (metaphor, allusion) show not only the language, but also the culture, history, and national identity of countries. Additionally, stylistic and rhetoric devices (attention-seeking devices, languaging, lexical borrowings, code switching, imperatives, ego targeting, rhetoric questions, superlatives, and other evaluative vocabulary) have another primary function in tourism discourse, which is to persuade the audience to visit or buy what is being promoted. Thus, linguoculturemes are the primary means of reflecting the culture via language in tourism discourse.

To sum up, Linguoculturology, being one of the modern fields of General Linguistics, has already become the center of contemporary anthropocentric research. It has attracted so many researchers, linguists and other scholars, thanks to its interdisciplinary character, making it relevant beyond Cultural Linguistics. Linguocultural analysis is usually conducted by identifying the linguoculturemes (culture-specific linguistic units) and their cultural connotations, which usually become basis for the relationship between language and culture. And, these linguocultural aspects of discourse are usually seen in such linguoculturemes as realia, lacunas, toponyms, metaphors, precedent phenomena, symbols, speech etiquette formulas, evaluative vocabulary, communicative strategies, and cultural concepts. As some aforementioned scholars suggested, linguocultural analysis is very relevant to discourse, as discourse is a dynamic space where culture is built and is represented within it. Furthermore,

discourse also reflects power, ideology, and all the cultural values of people with the help of (sometimes without) linguocultures. Therefore, be it a written or oral, formal or informal discourse, it always is charged with certain cultural connotations, usually carrying cultural information about participants of the communication or discourse. In other words, considering the fact that discourse encodes culturally specific values, behavioral standards, forms of address, social interaction models between communicants, and emotional patterns via lexical choices, communicative strategies, and symbolic senses, it is regarded as a complex communicative phenomenon that transmits culture, mentality, and worldview of nations. All of which means that discourse is not only analyzed linguistically, but we can analyze it at the conceptual, cognitive, pragmatic and symbolic levels, considering each type of discourse reflects distinct cultural information.

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